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Causes of Low Achievement of University' Students from Their Points of View

Kahtan Ahmed Al-Dahir, Al-Ahliyya Amman University, Jordan

Effects of School Type (Day School and Boarding School) on Secondary School Students' Academic Achievement in Social Studies

ODE, Dickson, Wesley High School, Nigeria

Interpreting Physics Teachers' Feedback Comments on Students' Solutions to Motion Tasks

¹Zahra Parvanehnezhad and ²Samson Madera Nashon, ¹Deakin University, Australia and ²University of British Columbia, Canada

Sipoc Model in Moroccan Engineering Education Context: Lean Approach

Amine Hadek, Hind Chaibate, Soumia Bakkali and Souad Ajana, Hassan Ii University Of Casablanca, Morocco

<https://airccse.com/ije/current2019.html>